

Investigation on the Fuel Properties of Blended Biodiesels and Its Impact on the Environment

O. Eboibi ✉

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Nigeria

W.O. Aki

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Nigeria

V.O. Aludu

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Ecological pollution has become a major public health concern, and the combustion of fossil fuels has been linked to environmental pollution. This has resulted in the formulation of more sustainable and eco-friendly fuels for internal combustion engines. In this study, traditional diesel was blended with biodiesels to mitigate the hazardous emissions, associated with the combustion of pure conventional diesel. Two major types of biodiesel - palm oil biodiesel (POB) and groundnut oil biodiesel (GOB) - were used for the laboratory investigation. They were blended with traditional diesel at ratios of 10%, 20%, and 30%. The blended biodiesels (BB) samples fuel properties and emission characteristics were tested in accordance with ASTM approved guidelines. The experimental outcomes indicated that the blending action had a significant influence on the properties and environmental friendliness of biodiesel. Notably, the CO emission levels from the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 biodiesel blends were 2.1, 1.7, 1.5, 1.9, 1.6 and 1.2 ppm, respectively; the NO₂ emission levels from the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 biodiesel blends were 103, 91, 79, 94, 85 and 71 ppm, respectively; and the SO₂ emission levels from the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 biodiesel blends were 15.8, 14.3, 13.5, 14.6, 13.9 and 13.1 ppm, respectively. This research's outcomes have highlighted that blended biodiesels emitted smaller volumes of CO, NO_x, and CO₂ during combustion. Interestingly, this study's findings have highlighted the effectiveness of biodiesel in achieving higher engine performance and enhancing ecological sustainability.

Keywords: Bio-fuel, energy security, engine performance, fuel combustion, public health.

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INTRODUCTION

Biodiesel is one of the sustainable green energies that is a suitable alternative to traditional (conventional) diesel. Typically, it is produced through the transesterification process, using plant-based and animal-based materials as the feedstock [1-3]. Biodiesel produced according to a standard can be successfully utilized in internal combustion diesel engines without modification or

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blending with fossil fuels to achieve maximum engine performance [4]. Currently, there is conventional energy insecurity due to the depleting fossil fuel reserves and persistent international conflicts (wars and internal crises), resulting in the drastic production and distribution of traditional fossil fuels [5,6].

The differences in the bioengineering properties and storage conditions of the feedstock used for biodiesel production usually affect its fuel properties and quality. This has led to the production of biodiesel with lower quality [7,8]. However, this challenge can be corrected through appropriate blending of the biodiesel with the right amount for traditional diesel, as this fortification process will enhance the fuel properties of the biodiesel [9-11]. Typically, traditional diesel blended biodiesel tends to high higher engine performance and fuel efficiency. This is due to the lower particulate matter (PM) and greenhouse gases these blended biodiesels (BB) emits during combustion [11-14].

Fuel combustion has been linked to carbon oxides (COx), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NOx), particulate matter, and other greenhouse gases [7]. These factors have been linked to the main sources of climate change and air quality deterioration [15,16]. Even though laboratory and practical investigations have established that biodiesels are more environmentally friendly than the fossil diesel, some environmental challenges still exist related to the emissions from these biodiesels. Some of these challenges include: respiratory diseases, cardiovascular problems, and other environmental dilapidation issues [17-19].

Scientific investigations have revealed that, blending biodiesel with appropriate volume of conventional diesel tends to produce a better environmentally friendly biodiesels with improved engine performance [10,14,20]. Additionally, [21] reported that properly formulated blended biodiesel (BB), tends to have far better fuel properties and integrity, and its attributes are immensely dependent on the design mix ratio of traditional diesel and biodiesel. It was also noted that blended biodiesels have considerably better public health attributes, due to their good emission characteristics and ecological impact [22]. "Though numerous studies have been carried out on the effectiveness of BB and its conservation friendliness, there is still a scarcity of information on the comprehensive emission characteristics of different BBs. Therefore, it is paramount to investigate this knowledge gap by evaluating the effectiveness, fuel properties, and emission characteristics of blended biodiesel formulated from different feedstocks. Notably, this study's findings will provide reliable information on the formulation of BBs, characterized by higher engine performance and a lower ecotoxicity level.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The two feedstocks used for this study's biodiesel production, were the groundnut oil and palm oil. These materials were chosen based on their high biodiesel yield and easy availability.

Reagents and instrumentations

The methanol, sodium hydroxide (NaOH), activated carbon, n-hexane, and homogenizers used for biodiesel production were of analytical grade. Additionally, the reactor vessel, stirring apparatus, laboratory hot plate, water bath, heating jacket, separation funnel, and drying columns were produced by Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., America.

Methods

Biodiesel Production

The biodiesel samples were produced by following standard procedures, using 85°C and at duration of one hour. 0.5% NaOH was used as the catalyst, while the methanol-to-oil ratio was set at 20%. The crude product was dried at 70°C for 60 minutes using a water bath, to obtain the refine (dried) biodiesel.

Biodiesel characterization

Tropically, the biodiesels samples were characterized using approved guidelines and equipment as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Method Used for the Biodiesel Characterization

Parameter	Method	Equipment
Acid value (AV)	AOCS–Cd 3d-63	Titration
Density	ASTM D4502	DMA 4500 M
Kinematic viscosity (KV)	DIN 12058	Lovis 2000 M/ME
Flash point (FP)	ASTM D93	CLA 5 Flash point tester
Boiling point (BP)	ASTM D86	Distillation apparatus
Sulphur content (SC)	ASTM D5453	UV Fluorescence Analyzer

Remarkably, the samples AV and density values were computed using approved expressions shown in Equations 1 and 2 [7].

$$AV = \frac{\text{titre}}{\text{Sample weight}} \times 5.61 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Sample weight}}{\text{Volume}} \quad (2)$$

Gaseous emission evaluation

The gaseous emissions during the fuel combustion were determined by utilizing the Emission Analyzer, which was calibrated to measure the amount of CO₂, CO, NO_x, SO_x, and particulate matter in the atmosphere. The experimental design mix used in this research is presented in Table 2. Basically, the palm oil biodiesel blend was coded “POB,” and the groundnut oil biodiesel blend was coded “GOB.”

Table 2. The Samples Coding

Sample code	Constituents
POB10	90% traditional diesel and 10% palm oil biodiesel
POB20	80% traditional diesel and 20% palm oil biodiesel
POB30	70% traditional diesel and 30% palm oil biodiesel
GOB10	90% traditional diesel and 10% groundnut oil biodiesel
GOB20	80% traditional diesel and 20% groundnut oil biodiesel
GOB30	70% traditional diesel and 30% groundnut oil biodiesel

Statistical Analysis

Results obtained in this research were statistically analyzed by employing the analysis of variance (ANOVA), to evaluate the effect of the blending ratio on the biodiesel fuel properties and emission characteristics. The means were separated using Duncan’s Multiple Range Tests at the 95% confidence level. Each test was repeated three times, and the calculated mean obtained was recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Biodiesel Fuel Properties

The fuel properties results for the two produced biodiesels are presented in Tables 3 and 4. The ANOVA result (Table 3) established that plant variety exhibits significant influence on some of their biodiesel fuel properties ($p \leq 0.05$). Likewise, the descriptive statistic showed in Table 4 reveals the summary results of the biodiesel’s density, AV, BP, FP, SC and KV values. It was noted that the palm biodiesel density, acid value, boiling point, flash point, sulfur content and viscosity values were

0.85 g/mL, 1.96%, 277.00°C, 194.33°C, 12.60 ppm and 4.51 mm/s², respectively. Equally, the groundnut oil biodiesel recorded density, AV, BP, FP, SC and viscosity values of 0.78 g/mL, 1.56 %, 258.33°C, 170.67°C, 11.33 ppm and 3.87 mm/s², respectively. These results revealed that the groundnut oil biodiesel generally had lower fuel properties than palm oil biodiesel. The study's findings indicate that the densities of biodiesels derived from palm oil and groundnut oil conform to the EN 14213 standard of 860 kg/m³, demonstrating their suitability as biodiesel fuels. However, the acid values obtained for both biodiesels exceeded the limits specified by ASTM D6751 (0.05%) and EN 14213 (0.5%), respectively.

Remarkably, the higher AV recorded in this study is an indication that the fuel samples have higher free fatty acid levels. This situation may result in severe corrosion of the metallic components of the engine system that are in contact with fuel, thereby reducing the biodiesel's integrity and usability [7,23]. It was further deduced from the outcomes that the plant variety played a significant role in the biodiesel acidity level, affirming the earlier report by [24], which stated that the variety plays a major role in plant engineering properties. It can be seen that the findings of this research indicate that the biodiesel samples exhibited higher flash point values, exceeding the recommended EN 14213 standard value of 120°C. This limitation appears to be specific to this study, as similar findings of elevated flash points have been documented by other scholars [25,26].

Table 3. One-Way ANOVA of the Effect Biodiesel Types on Their Fuel Properties

Parameter		SS	df	Mean Square	F	P value
Density	Between Groups	.007	1	0.007	7.273	0.054 ^{ns}
	Within Groups	.004	4	0.001		
	Total	0.010	5			
Acid value	Between Groups	0.240	1	0.240	48.000	0.002*
	Within Groups	0.020	4	0.005		
	Total	0.260	5			
Boiling point	Between Groups	522.667	1	522.667	23.059	0.009*
	Within Groups	90.667	4	22.667		
	Total	613.333	5			
Flash point	Between Groups	840.167	1	840.167	18.331	0.013*
	Within Groups	183.333	4	45.833		
	Total	1023.500	5			
Sulphur content	Between Groups	2.394	1	2.394	2.298	0.204 ^{ns}
	Within Groups	4.168	4	1.042		
	Total	6.562	5			
Viscosity	Between Groups	0.608	1	0.608	11.678	.027
	Within Groups	0.208	4	0.052		
	Total	0.816	5			

Note: POB = palm oil biodiesel, GOB = groundnut oil biodiesel, * = significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) according to DMRT

Table 4. The Descriptive Summary of the Biodiesels Fuel Properties

Parameter	Biodiesel type	N	Mean	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
Density (g/mL)	POB	3	0.85	0.02	0.82	0.88
	GOB	3	0.78	0.02	0.75	0.81
Acid value (%)	POB	3	1.96	0.08	1.89	1.97
	GOB	3	1.56	0.04	1.49	1.64
Boiling point (°C)	POB	3	277.00	3.46	271.00	283.00
	GOB	3	258.33	1.76	255.00	261.00
Flash point (°C)	POB	3	194.33	4.06	187.00	201.00
	GOB	3	170.67	3.76	164.00	177.00
Sulfur content (ppm)	POB	3	12.59	0.69	11.75	13.98
	GOB	3	11.33	0.46	10.53	12.11
Viscosity (mm ² /s)	POB	3	4.51	0.14	4.26	4.75
	GOB	3	3.87	0.12	3.66	4.08

The Blended Biodiesels Fuel Properties

The fuel properties results obtained for the BB specimens are presented in Table 5. The densities of the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20 and GOB30 were 0.801, 0.812, 0.827, 0.771, 0.779 and 0.784 g/cm³, respectively. This is an indication that the BB sample developed density values, which is inversely proportional to the volume of the traditional diesel in the product. This observation aligns with the earlier findings reported by [25], during their investigation into green energy applications. This situation (density-related behavioral pattern) can be linked to a relatively higher density of biodiesel (Table 3) compared to fossil diesel. Notably, this elevated BBs density will have a significant impact on fuel combustion effectiveness and engine efficiency [27].

Table 5 highlighted that the acid values of the biodiesel blends POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 were 1.517, 1.562, 1.615, 1.386, 1.421, and 1.536%, respectively. These findings depicted that the BB acidity declined slightly, with the introduction of fresh traditional diesel into the biodiesel. Biodiesel usually acquires its high acidity through factors such as crop type, poor processing operations - which can lead to incomplete reactions during transesterification, and the presence of impurities in the biodiesel [7]. This higher acidity is detrimental to biodiesel efficiency; hence, the formulation of BBs should be optimized to reduce the product's acidity. This will result in BBs with higher quality standards and improved fuel efficiency [28].

Furthermore, the kinematic viscosity values of the biodiesel blends of POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 were 4.116, 4.183, 4.231, 3.288, 3.297 and 3.013 mm/s², respectively. This depicted that the BBs viscosity recorded a slight increment, due to the increase in the biodiesel volume in the BB product. Kinematic viscosity is among the essential fuel properties that affect fuel atomization, as well as the internal combustion engine performance [29]. Scientific investigations have revealed that, fuel having higher KV values tends to cause fuel injector malfunction, leading to incomplete combustion and fuel wastage [25]. Additionally, the flash point values of the biodiesel blends of POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 were 138, 145, 149, 125, 129 and 134°C, respectively. While the sulfur content values of the biodiesel blends of POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 were 8.15, 8.83, 9.21, 7.83, 8.46 and 8.89 ppm, respectively. This study's findings have revealed that BBs flash point increases in a non-linear pattern as the biodiesel volume in the blends increases. The higher flash point of the BBs is advantageous because it will make the fuel safer for storage and handling operations [29]. Remarkably, the results portrays that the sulfur content of the BBs slightly increases with an increment in the biodiesel volume in the blended products, but the values were within the acceptable range, signifying the ecological benefits of the BBs. Lower SC levels in biofuel result in reducing the emission of toxic sulfur oxides during combustion [30,31].

Table 5. The Blended Biodiesels Fuel Properties

Parameter	POB 10	POB 20	POB 30	GOB 10	GOB 20	GOB 30
Density (g/cm ³)	0.801	0.812	0.827	0.771	0.779	0.784
Acid value	1.517	1.562	1.615	1.386	1.421	1.536
kinematic viscosity (mm/S ²)	4.116	4.183	4.231	3.288	3.297	3.013
Flash point (°C)	138	145	149	125	129	134
Sulfur content (ppm)	8.15	8.83	9.21	7.83	8.46	8.89

Blended Biodiesel Exhaust Emission Analysis

Table 6 presents the results of the gaseous emissions of the BBs during combustion. The CO₂ emission levels from the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 biodiesel blends were 7.9, 7.2, 6.3, 7.1, 6.3 and 5.4 ppm, respectively. The NO₂ emission levels from the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 biodiesel blends were 103, 91, 79, 94, 85 and 71 ppm, respectively. Additionally, the CO emission levels from the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 biodiesel blends were 2.1, 1.7, 1.5, 1.9, 1.6 and 1.2 ppm, respectively. Furthermore, the SO₂ emission levels from the POB10, POB20, POB30, GOB10, GOB20, and GOB30 biodiesel blends were 15.8, 14.3, 13.5, 14.6, 13.9 and 13.1 ppm, respectively. These findings specify that the volume of CO₂ emitted is inversely proportional to the volume of biodiesel in the BBs.

Comparatively, POB exhibited higher CO₂ emissions than GOB, consistent with observations reported by [28]. The inconsistency in the results documented for both the POB BBs and GOB BBs in this research, can be attributed to the greater fatty acid levels in the POB (Table 4). Despite some limitations, the findings of this investigation have shown some prospects for the BBs formulated in this study in reducing CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion.

Furthermore, the outcomes of this research have highlighted that the volume of NO₂ discharged during combustion declined non-linearly as the volume of biodiesel in the mix design decreased. This aligned with the earlier findings documented by [27] on biodiesel efficiency. Similarly, the smaller amounts of CO and SO₂ liberated during fuel combustion can be associated with more complete combustion of the blended fuel [30]. Precisely, the results reflected that the GOB-based fuel samples discharged less SO₂ than the POB-based samples. This may be attributed to the differences in the GOB and POB physiochemical properties and antioxidant compositions. Antioxidants play essential roles in facilitating the complete combustion of biofuels, and inhibiting the oxidation of fuel properties [28]. Remarkably, this study's findings have highlighted the environmental benefits of blending traditional diesel with appropriate biodiesel. "This will lead to the production of enriched diesel with lower emissions of toxic gases during fuel combustion. Primarily, this is due to the verified amounts of CO, CO₂, NO₂, and SO₂ emitted during combustion, resulting in an improved environmental protection and engine performance.

Table 6. The Blended Biodiesels Emission Quality

	POB blend			GOB blend		
	10%	20%	30%	10%	20%	30%
CO ₂	7.9	7.2	6.3	7.1	6.3	5.4
NO ₂	103	91	79	94	85	71
CO	2.1	1.7	1.5	1.9	1.6	1.2
SO ₂	15.8	14.3	13.5	14.6	13.9	13.1

CONCLUSION

This research was embarked upon to appraise the impact of blending fossil diesel with different volumes of biodiesel. Palm oil biodiesel (POB) and groundnut oil biodiesel (GOB) were used to blend with traditional diesel, using different mix design ratios. The fuel properties and combustion emission characteristics of the resultant blended biodiesel samples were tested in accordance with standard procedures. Typically, from the results analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Groundnut oil biodiesel has better fuel properties than palm oil biodiesel.
2. Conventional diesel blended with 30% biodiesel emitted the lowest CO gas.
3. The 10% biodiesel blends (BBs) emitted in the maximum CO gas.
4. Conventional diesel blended with 30% biodiesel emitted the minimum CO₂.
5. The 10% BBs produced the maximum CO₂
6. The 30% BBs emitted the lowest NO₂ gas.
7. Conventional diesel blended with 10% biodiesel yielded the highest NO₂ gas.
8. Conventional diesel blended with 30% biodiesel yielded the minimum SO₂ gas, and
9. The 10% BBs produced the maximum SO₂ gas

RECOMMENDATIONS

These recommendations were made after the discussion of results:

1. This study utilized only two types of biodiesels, therefore similar experiments should be conducted where more biodiesels can be hybridized

2. The design mix ratio consists of only three blending ratios, therefore future research should be carried out with more blending, so that robust data can be achieved.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Sajjad et al., "Biodiesel Production from Alkali-Catalyzed Transesterification of Tamarindus indica Seed Oil and Optimization of Process Conditions," *Molecules*, vol. 27, no. 10, p. 3230, 2022, doi: 10.3390/molecules27103230.
- [2] S. Sherkhanov, T. P. Korman, S. G. Clarke, and J. U. Bowie, "Production of FAME biodiesel in *E. coli* by direct methylation with an insect enzyme," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 6, p. 24239, 2016, doi: 10.1038/srep24239.
- [3] D. Neupane, "Biofuels from Renewable Sources, a Potential Option for Biodiesel Production," *Bioengineering*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 29, 2023, doi: 10.3390/bioengineering10010029.
- [4] N. E. Benti et al., "Biodiesel production in Ethiopia: Current status and future prospects," *Sci. Afr.*, vol. 19, p. e01531, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.sciaf.2022.e01531.
- [5] A. Mayer, "Fossil fuel dependence and energy insecurity," *Energy Sustain. Soc.*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 9, 2022, doi: 10.1186/s13705-022-00353-5.
- [6] O. J. Olujobi, U. E. Okorie, E. S. Olarinde, and A. D. Aina-Pelemo, "Legal responses to energy security and sustainability in Nigeria's power sector amidst fossil fuel disruptions and low carbon energy transition," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 7, p. e17912, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17912.
- [7] O. Eboibi, E. O. Edafiadhe, and H. Uguru, "Comparative analysis of the fuel properties of biodiesel produced from different groundnut varieties," *Int. J. Adv. Acad. Res.*, vol. 8, no. 9, pp. 10–23, 2022.
- [8] E. J. Sinebe and H. Uguru, "The Effects of Plants Essential Oils on Biodiesel Fuel Properties during Storage," *IPS J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 70–74, 2025, doi: 10.541117/ijet.v1i2.15.
- [9] A. K. Sharma, P. K. Sharma, V. Chintala, N. Khatri, and A. Patel, "Environment-Friendly Biodiesel/Diesel Blends for Improving the Exhaust Emission and Engine Performance to Reduce the Pollutants Emitted from Transportation Fleets," *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 11, p. 3896, 2020, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17113896.
- [10] M. Hawrot-Paw, A. Koniuszy, G. Zając, and J. Szyszlak-Bargłowicz, "Ecotoxicity of soil contaminated with diesel fuel and biodiesel," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 16436, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-73469-3.
- [11] S. O. Okpo and E. D. Edafiadhe, "Unlocking the Power of Waste Cooking Oils for Sustainable Energy Production and Circular Economy: A Review," *ABUAD J. Eng. Res. Dev.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 41–55, 2024, doi: 10.53982/ajerd.2024.0701.05-j.
- [12] N. A. Amran, U. Bello, and M. S. Hazwan Ruslan, "The role of antioxidants in improving biodiesel's oxidative stability, poor cold flow properties, and the effects of the duo on engine performance: A review," *Heliyon*, vol. 8, no. 7, p. e09846, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09846.
- [13] M. A. Hazrat et al., "A Mini Review on the Cold Flow Properties of Biodiesel and its Blends," *Front. Energy Res.*, vol. 8, p. 598651, 2020, doi: 10.3389/fenrg.2020.598651.
- [14] P. Oghenerukewve, U. Asibeluo, F. Odoh, G. Okolotu, and H. Uguru, "Determination of the impact of essential oil on the oxidation stability and electrical properties of biodiesel," *Irish Int. J. Eng. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1–12, 2024.
- [15] I. Manisalidis, E. Stavropoulou, A. Stavropoulos, and E. Bezirtzoglou, "Environmental and Health Impacts of Air Pollution: A Review," *Front. Public Health*, vol. 8, p. 14, 2020, doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2020.00014.
- [16] A. Afifa, K. Arshad, N. Hussain, M. H. Ashraf, and M. Z. Saleem, "Air pollution and climate change as grand challenges to sustainability," *Sci. Total Environ.*, vol. 928, p. 172370, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172370.

- [17] H. K. Jeswani, A. Chilvers, and A. Azapagic, "Environmental sustainability of biofuels: a review," *Proc. R. Soc. A*, vol. 476, no. 2243, p. 20200351, 2020, doi: 10.1098/rspa.2020.0351.
- [18] T. Khanam et al., "Environmental sustainability assessment of biodiesel production from *Jatropha curcas* L. seeds oil in Pakistan," *PLoS One*, vol. 16, no. 11, p. e0258409, 2021, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0258409.
- [19] J. Zhang, "Energy access challenge and the role of fossil fuels in meeting electricity demand: Promoting renewable energy capacity for sustainable development," *Geosci. Front.*, vol. 15, no. 5, p. 101873, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.gsf.2024.101873.
- [20] K. R. Shivanna, "Climate change and its impact on biodiversity and human welfare," *Proc. Indian Natl. Sci. Acad. A Phys. Sci.*, vol. 88, no. 2, pp. 160–171, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s43538-022-00073-6.
- [21] S. Rajendran et al., "Enhancing Performance and Emission Characteristics of Biodiesel-Operated Compression Ignition Engines through Low Heat Rejection Mode and Antioxidant Additives: A Review," *ACS Omega*, vol. 8, no. 38, pp. 34281–34298, 2023, doi: 10.1021/acsomega.3c03252.
- [22] A. Aljaafari, I. M. R. Fattah, M. I. Jahirul, Y. Gu, T. M. I. Mahlia, M. A. Islam, and M. S. Islam, "Biodiesel Emissions: A State-of-the-Art Review on Health and Environmental Impacts," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 18, p. 6854, 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15186854.
- [23] S. M. Farouk, A. M. Tayeb, and S. M. S. Abdel-Hamid, "Recent advances in transesterification for sustainable biodiesel production, challenges, and prospects: a comprehensive review," *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*, vol. 31, pp. 12722–12747, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11356-024-32027-4.
- [24] A. Amitabh et al., "Development and Performance Evaluation of Watermelon Pulper Based on Mechanical Action of Crushing and Shearing Force," *J. Biobased Mater. Bioenergy*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 375–382, 2023.
- [25] A. Khalid, N. Tamaldin, M. Jaat, M. F. M. Ali, B. Manshoor, and I. Zaman, "Impacts of Biodiesel Storage Duration on Fuel Properties and Emissions," *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 68, pp. 225–230, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.proeng.2013.12.172.
- [26] M. Kiehadroudzehad, A. Merabet, C. Ghenai, A. G. Abo-Khalil, and T. Salameh, "The role of biofuels for sustainable Microgrids: A path towards carbon neutrality and the green economy," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. e13407, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13407.
- [27] A. A. Yusuf et al., "A quantitative comparison of economic viability, volatile organic compounds, and particle-bound carbon emissions from a diesel engine fueled with biodiesel blends," *Measurement: Energy*, vol. 3, p. 100017, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.meae.2024.100017.
- [28] I. M. Hadi, I. S. Sintali, H. Dandakouta, and A. Tokan, "Performance characteristics of clove oil, eugenol and eugenyl acetate as bio-additives in a single cylinder diesel engine," *Saudi J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 6, no. 8, pp. 275–289, 2021.
- [29] V. Arya and C. Shrivastava, "Performance Evaluation of Biodiesel Blends from Mahua, *Jatropha*, and Neem Oils in Diesel Engines: A Comprehensive Review," *Int. J. Res. Publ. Rev.*, vol. 5, no. 7, pp. 3564–3570, 2024, doi: 10.55248/gengpi.5.0724.1923.
- [30] U. Rajak and T. N. Verma, "Effect of emission from ethylic biodiesel of edible and non-edible vegetable oil, animal fats, waste oil and alcohol in CI engine," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 166, pp. 704–718, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2018.04.070.
- [31] H. Xu, L. Ou, Y. Li, T. R. Hawkins, and M. Wang, "Life Cycle Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Biodiesel and Renewable Diesel Production in the United States," *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 56, no. 12, pp. 7512–7521, 2022, doi: 10.1021/acs.est.2c00289.
- [32] K. D. Mekonnen, Y. A. Endris, and K. Y. Abdu, "Alternative Methods for Biodiesel Cetane Number Valuation: A Technical Note," *ACS Omega*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 6296–6304, 2024, doi: 10.1021/acsomega.3c09216.

